

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Method is how far Helpful for the Learners in the Context of Bangladesh

Ferdousi Akter^{1*}

¹ Department of English, Islamic University of Kushtia, Bangladesh

Accepted Feb 09,2021

Published March,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Ferdousi Akter

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4574657>

Pages: 328-335

Funding: Self.

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article

(APA): Ferdousi Akter (2021). Analysis of the Educational Impact of M-Learning and Related. *North American Academic Research*, 4(2), 328-335. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4574657>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

CLT is one of the best Language Teaching Methods as it can improve the communication skill in the smartest way. Adopting different methods for developing the language teaching is not new in Bangladesh, and CLT is the latest addition. This method was adopted in Bangladesh in the 90s for developing the English Communication Skill of the secondary and higher secondary level students. In the light of this method, some conspicuous changes brought in the textbooks and question papers of those levels. All these changes are effective in stepping up the communication skill, but some severe problems exist in implementing this much acclaimed method.

Keywords: ICT, KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY, LITERATURE REVIEW, MOBILELEARNING, MULTIMEDIA MOBILE DEVICES

Introduction

As a social being, it is obvious for every man to communicate with one other. We can smoothly communicate with any people in our Mother Language as we all learned the language from our birth. And a person can rightly express his or her opinion in the Mother Language. But, not all people around the world speak in only one language, and obviously their language will not be the same. Different languages have emerged in this globe because of the different geographical, social, cultural events that exist in different areas. So, to communicate with such people who don't speak in our

own language, we need to learn his language. But learning all the languages that prevailed in different countries is not possible at all by a single man.

To fix this issue world community set one language (English) in which people can do the necessary communication with the people who are not familiar with one's mother language. So Non Native English Speaking countries now try to make their citizens adapt to communicate in English as a second language through their educational institutions. That's why different methods have emerged to make such communicative learning smarter. CLT is one of those methods that the different educational institutions of Bangladesh now apply, like other Non Native English Speaking countries. Like any other method or system,

there are some merits and demerits, and some aspects of it are not well effective for the learners in Bangladeshi educational institutions now. Fixing these issues rightly will obviously ease the understanding and learning the Communicative English well.

Objective

The objective of this study was to find out the barriers that prevent the effective implementation of the CLT method. If the method is properly implemented in the secondary and higher secondary level educational institutions, every learner's performance in English will obviously be excellent. But a good many relevant newspaper reports over the years has shown otherwise, which should be looked into immediately. Finding out all the evils behind such shocking images and possible solutions for rightly implementing the CLT method, is the objective of this study.

Methodology of the Study

This study entitled "Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Method is How Far Helpful for The Learners in The Context of Bangladesh" is mainly based on the secondary sources. To examine the implementation level of CLT, I have thoroughly examined the textbook and question papers of secondary and higher secondary level, where CLT was applied. Different aspects relating to the CLT method have been mentioned here in the light of several well-known books on Language Teaching Methods. To represent some relevant current issues, I have gone through several wide circulated newspapers, which I mentioned here.

Limitation of The Study

Actually in Bangladesh, there's scarcity of well trained personalities who have specialized means of knowledge on the CLT method. So I had to depend on the books written by foreign scholars, though the study-conducting area was Bangladesh. Those scholars gave the suggestions and recommendations based on the education system of their countries which are obviously a bit different from that of Bangladesh.

ELEMENTARY DISCUSSION ON LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): What it really is?

This is a method that focuses on the interaction in a foreign language, and its other name is Communicative Approach. In teaching this method, the teacher's ultimate goal is to grow the student's ability to communicate in target language. Memorizing bunches of grammar rules, or something like that is not the way of this teaching method. But it is not learning without grammar as "communicative competence does not mean an absence of grammar instruction but rather grammar instruction that leads to the ability to communicate effectively."ⁱ

"Communicative language teaching (CLT) refers to both processes and goals in classroom learning. The central theoretical concept in communicative language teaching is 'communicative competence, a term introduced into discussions of language use and second or foreign language learning in the early 1970s."ⁱⁱ

Besides the Reading & Writing like the old fashioned teaching, Speaking & Listening gets importance here.

Commonly CLT applying teachers follow some ways of teaching like Role-play, Interviews, Group Work,

Opinion Sharing, and the like. By successfully doing these, students can speak in English fluently in their day to day life, like a common native English speaker.

“One of the goals of CLT is to develop fluency in language use. Fluency is natural language use occurring when a speaker engages in meaningful interaction and maintains comprehensible and ongoing communication despite limitations in his or her communicative competence. Fluency is developed by creating classroom activities in which students must negotiate meaning, use communication strategies, correct misunderstandings, and work to avoid communication breakdowns.”ⁱⁱⁱ

Other Second Language Teaching Methods besides CLT

Teaching a foreign language is now a common phenomenon in almost all the non-native English speaking countries. The CLT method has now prevailed all over those countries due to some amazing advantages of this method. Besides the CLT method, there are several methods for teaching a second language, and these are given below-

- 1) Grammar Translation Method (GTM):** It focuses on the study of grammar rules, and making translation from one language to the target language, or vice-versa. In this method, speaking gets a little importance in comparison with the other methods.
- 2) Direct Method (DM):** It is opposite to the GTM as here the studying grammar gets a little importance. This method contains an “immediate and audio visual association” and gives utmost importance on the meaning, context, and pronunciation.
- 3) Audio-lingual Method:** This method emerged during the Second World War and it contains the repeated “oral practice” of something in the target language. In other words, language teaching through this method involves listening and speaking of a foreign language repeatedly.

There were some problems in implementing the above mentioned three methods, and that’s why scholars got dissatisfied. At last borrowing some much acclaimed ideas of different methods, they introduced the CLT method, and till now it’s the best.

CLT METHOD: BANGLADESH PERSPECTIVE

Introducing The CLT Method in Bangladesh

Actually this method was first developed in the 1970s in some countries other than Bangladesh, and after almost two decades it was introduced in Bangladesh. In the 90s, the Ministry of Education introduced this system in the secondary and higher secondary level through a project named English Language Teaching Improvement Project (ELTIP).

“English Language Teaching Improvement Project (ELTIP), jointly funded by the Government of Bangladesh and Department for International Development (DFID) of the UK in cooperation with National Curriculum Textbook Board (NCTB), started working to facilitate teaching and learning of English in Bangladesh as soon as new language teaching approach was adopted. It paid significant attention to CLT and introduced the approach in the national English curriculum of the country for the first time in 1990s.

From 1997, the communicative English tasks were introduced in the compulsory English Textbooks for secondary and higher secondary level students in Bangladesh.”^{iv}

From then on, the CLT is the English learning method in secondary and higher secondary level (from class VI to XII). But with the passage of time several topics have been introduced in the English Textbooks of these levels, but CLT remains the teaching method.

Present Application of CLT Method in Bangladesh

In the secondary and higher secondary levels, now there are three public examinations (with some equivalent others) named- Junior School Certificate (JSC), Secondary School Certificate (SSC), and Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC). In these levels, the English textbooks are now in two papers- first and second papers. In the first paper book, there are some short stories, poems, or something like that. First paper question includes one seen comprehension (to answer some MCQ like questions), rearranging, paragraph/letter writing, completing story, etc. And in the second paper question, there are two parts- Grammar and Composition.

But the saddest reality is that there’s no room for developing the speaking and listening skill, though the CLT method gives utmost importance on these two. The English textbooks are designed keeping the CLT method in mind and keeping all the terms commonly used in day to day communication, but this is not greatly helpful in developing the skill for smooth communication. Even the teachers of secondary and higher secondary level have almost no specialised training for developing communication skills in English. “Bangladesh is one of the few countries where a person can start teaching without any specialised training. Mammoth projects like formulating new curriculum, developing communicative textbooks and teachers’ guide will prove ineffective if these teachers are not trained adequately to utilise these innovations.”^v

TAKING A LOOK ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CLT IN BANGLADESH

Is This Method Appropriate for Bangladesh?

The CLT method is the best language teaching method in the world there’s no gainsaying in it. It also has some cons but the number of those is obviously lower in comparison with similar other systems. But to enjoy the sheer benefit of this system, some conditions must be fulfilled. These conditions include having sufficient number of trained teachers, lower number of students in a class, scope for oral practicing, and the like. But, unfortunately, Bangladesh doesn’t have any of those and there’s no continuous attempt to change the situation. Suppose the CLT method was first formally introduced in Bangladesh through the English Language Teaching Improvement Project (ELTIP) project. This project was for training a group of teachers about the CLT method, but this project couldn’t become successful due to fund shortage.

“The ELTIP followed introduction of CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) as new syllabus prescribed.....Sixty-two satellite units were opened under seven regional resource centres in the country to facilitate training for 79000 high school teachers. The first phase of the project from 1999 to 2002 included trainers’ training abroad, setting up of regional and satellite resource centres and training of about 5000 teachers. Due to fund shortage, all targeted teachers could not be brought under the training

programme during the period. A source in the project said that only 17 out of 62 satellite resource centres and four out of seven regional centres could be opened in districts. Out of the 17 satellite centres, only six were set up in six districts of Pabna, Noagoan, Bogra, Nilphamari, Rangpur and Dinajpur. The extended project aimed at training 42000 school teachers. But it failed to achieve the target due to shortage of resources. Only 7000 teachers could be brought under the programme in the second phase.”^{vi}

Is it wise to hope for better outcomes from a system while the system applying persons are not well-trained? Certainly not, and it’s the saddest reality that, in Bangladesh, educational institutions can’t provide sufficient numbers of teachers who have at least basic training on applying the CLT method. To apply rightly the CLT method, the participation of the learners in the oral practicing session is a must. But due to the higher number of learners in almost all the institutions, it’s not possible at all. “In line with the Education Policy, the teacher-student ratio at both primary and secondary levels was determined as 1:30. But, the teacher-student ratio is now 1:37 at the primary level and 1:45 at the secondary level, which is quite worrying. Joyful learning is hardly possible in a large size of class. So, an ideal classroom size is essential.”^{vii}

So a teacher cannot interact with such a huge number of learners in a class of one hour or so. Such a classroom is not the place where a teacher can arrange a participatory oral practicing session in English. English textbooks are published by The National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB) in line with the CLT method, but till now, Bangladeshi education system can’t create a proper environment for effectively implementing the method. So till now, Bangladesh is fully ready to adopt the CLT method and adopt the same successfully.

How Far The CLT Method is Helpful for The Learners in Bangladesh at Current Times?

“Communicative language teaching involves letting go of certain roles that both teachers and students bring to the classroom as part of their implicit socialization in the educative process.....Communication involves more than just speaking; it is a complex act that is context-dependent and that varies in purpose. One context is the classroom, and teachers cannot replicate the outside world in the classroom.”^{viii} But the reality in Bangladesh is that educational institutions at secondary and higher secondary level don’t have enough arrangements to provide an oral practicing friendly environment. That’s why enjoying proper helpfulness from this method is unthinkable in such a situation.

For that reason, after passing the higher secondary level a good many students cannot show desired performance in English in other examinations. A few years ago, Dhaka University’s B Unit (Kha) admission test result showed the real image of the student’s skill in English. “Poor quality of teaching at the secondary and higher secondary levels has led to the disastrous English examination results in the Dhaka University’s 'Kha' unit admission test, says Prof Serajul Islam Choudhury. Of the total 40,565 examinees, 22,000 failed in English and only two students qualified to be enrolled in the university’s English department for the 2014-15 session, according to university sources. This time, the university had made it compulsory for the applicants to obtain at least 15 marks in 'Elective English', apart from getting the usual 20 marks in the general English, to be enrolled in the department. The students did not do good in English in the previous university

admission tests as well. In 2013-14 session, 56 percent of 36,836 students failed in the subject in the 'Kha' unit admission test, records show.”^{ix}

This incident sufficiently shows how much helpful the current system is for developing the performance in English. There are some conspicuous problems in rightly implementing the CLT method. But that doesn't mean learners don't get any advantages from this method. After introducing the CLT method in the secondary and higher secondary level, English textbooks and question papers have been changed in the light of the method. Suppose in English first paper, there're questions like dialogue writing, completing story, summary writing, and the like. And, in the English second paper question of SSC and HSC, there're now 60 marks in Grammar. In these questions, topics which are necessary for running the day to day communication have been kept. Among those, questions relating to the right form of verbs, completing sentences using clauses/phrases, changing sentences according to given direction, etc have been brought. All these are designed according to the CLT method, and obviously these topics keep an important role in developing the communication skill in English. We can't deny the role of these topics in developing communication skills, but at the same time it is also true that there are some other questions in the question paper which are not in line with the CLT method. Suppose in the English questions of secondary and higher secondary level, there're questions like paragraph or essay writing. Students just memorise some common paragraphs and essays before exam, and in the exam, they write down the sentences which they memorised. By doing so, they just get some easy marks but this practice will not develop the communication skill at all.

As the educational institutions don't create a system in which every learner has to participate in the oral practice, we cannot hope for the full helpfulness from the CLT method. But inserting some topics in the light of the method helps learners to understand and use the terms we commonly use in our day to day communication. So, it can be said that current application of the CLT method is effective for learners to a very limited extent.

SIMPLE WAY TO MAKE THE CLT MUCH HELPFUL METHOD

Training The Teachers and Banning The Guidebooks-Using will be Helpful for The Learners

The learners don't get the full avails of the CLT method now mainly because of two long standing problems that existed in most of the parts of Bangladesh. These two are the imposing guidebook by some coaching centres, and implementing the CLT method by the teachers without proper training. If we can fix these two, the learners will obviously get desired benefits from this method.

On 2009, the widely circulated newspaper The Daily Star published a report on the banning of Guidebooks by Apex Court, the report reads- “The Supreme Court (SC) yesterday cleared the way for enforcement of the ban on printing, publishing, import, distribution and sale of guidebooks and notebooks for primary and secondary school students. The apex court upheld the High Court (HC) verdict that allowed the government to take action in case of violation of the ban.”^x But after 2 years from that order the same newspaper published another report on the same issue, which reads- “Illegal notebooks and guidebooks, printed by some unscrupulous publishers, have flooded the markets in Barisal and Khulna districts. A number of

publishers printed the textbooks secretly and selling those on the markets. Those deprived of getting textbooks are being deceived after buying the printed books of the companies.”^{xi}

So the situation has not been changed according to the guideline provided by the Apex Court as still a huge number of students are guidebooks dependent, especially for memorising the composition part. This is the most important barrier for implementing the CLT method rightly as in that case students don't try to develop their communication skill in English. Rather they just try to memorise some sentences and write them down in the answer script.

CLT is not a method for providing some information to the learners, but here the teacher's role is like a facilitator who will help the learners to develop their communication skill. As the method is relatively new in this country, training on this method is a must. A teacher can't learn the correct implementation of the method through reading some books rather he must know how to interact with the students effectively. That's why training for implementing the CLT method must be started immediately, and passing at least one training course should be made mandatory for all the English Teachers at the secondary and higher secondary level. With the inclusion of the CLT method, after all, the textbooks standard is up to mark now. But two things- guidebook dependency and implementing without training make all the efforts for implementing CLT, just a mismatch. So solving these two problems will obviously eradicate the barriers which prevent the proper implementation of the CLT method.

Concluding Comment on The CLT Method in Bangladesh

Like every learning method, the CLT method has some demerits, but the number of those is relatively lower. Bangladeshi educational institutions adopted the CLT method in English textbooks more than twenty years ago, but the proper implementation has not been till now. If it could be implemented perfectly, the performance of previous learners would obviously be outstanding. The poor performance shown by the students after passing higher secondary level is sufficient to represent the ugly truth- it has not been implemented perfectly. Obviously introducing the method develops the communication skill to some extent, but to reach the desired level, still a long way to go.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Jack C. Richards : Communicative Language Teaching Today
2. James F. Lee and Bill VanPatten : Making Communicative Language Teaching Happen
3. Sandra j. Savignon : Communicative Language Teaching: Linguistic Theory

ⁱ Masum Billah, CLT What Really Happens In Our Classrooms?, November 25, 2020, The New Nation, (m.thedailynewnation.com/news/269922/clt-what-really-happens-in-our-classrooms)

-
- ii Sandra j. Savignon, *Communicative Language Teaching: Linguistic Theory and Classroom Practice*, Mary Jane Peluso, p. 1
- iii Jack C. Richards, *Communicative Language Teaching Today*, Cambridge University Press, 2006, p. 14
- iv Iqbal-e-Rasul, *The Situation of Communicative Language Teaching Approach in Bangladesh – An Assessment*, *UITS Journal* Volume: 5 Issue: 1, p. 24, (<https://uits.edu.bd/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/02-The-Situation-of-Communicative-23-32.pdf>)
- v Md Shahnawaz Khan Chandan, *Curing The Fear of English*, November 11, 2016, *The Daily Star* (<https://www.thedailystar.net/star-weekend/education/curing-the-fear-english-1312993>)
- vi Fund shortage to stop ELTIP, *The Daily Star*, December 21, 2004 (<http://archive.thedailystar.net/2004/12/21/d41221070377.htm>)
- vii Md Enamul Hoque, *Making learning joyful*, Dec 05, 2020, *The New Age* (<https://www.newagebd.net/article/123419/making-learning-joyful>)
- viii James F. Lee and Bill VanPatten, *Making Communicative Language Teaching Happen*, McGraw-Hill Education, Second Edition, p. 2
- ix Poor English teaching quality raises concern, *The Daily Star*, September 27, 2014 (<https://www.thedailystar.net/poor-english-teaching-quality-raises-concern-43529>)
- x Guidebook ban to stay, *The Daily Star*, December 09, 2009(<https://www.thedailystar.net/news-detail-117103>)
- xi Illegal notebooks flood Barisal, Khulna markets, *The Daily Star*, January 18, 2012, (<https://www.thedailystar.net/news-detail-218861>)

Ferdousi Akter, Assistant Professor, Dept. of English, Islamic University, Kushtia, Bangladesh, Email:ferdousipritey21@gmail.com

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

